

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th June 2021

Accepted: 10th June 2021

Online: 15th June 2021

KEY WORDS

education,
standard
,prerequisite,
urgent,history

OVERVIEW OF AFGHANISTAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4985910>

ABSTRACT

Historically, higher levels of learning failed to receive due attention in Afghanistan, and while the institutions started taking roots in last half of the 21st century, their progress was badly hampered by foreign aggression likewise as infighting. In recent years, there are some efforts for improvement. However, educational activity in present day Afghanistan remains a fragile area, hugely dependent upon foreign assistance, having meager resources and feeble infrastructure, importantly, the system of upper education being promoted isn't in conformity with the normal and non-secular value system of the country.

Standard of education being imparted also remains very low. While long-term peace could be a prerequisite, there's an urgent must deliberate upon the system of education, particularly at higher levels, and therefore the foundations upon which it's to be established.

Overview of Afghan Education Structure:

The history of Afghan school education dates back to its very elementary and old Mosques and Madrasa-based system. People familiar to urge Islamic education from the clerics (Mullahs) in mosques and Madrasa which remain as traditional education centers within the Afghan community. The new education system was founded at the tip of the 19th century for the first time. In 1878, two schools for contemporary education were in-built Kabul, the capital city of Afghanistan. These two schools were one

army and one universal school. Later, in 1903 another highschool was established with but ten Afghan and Indian teachers. But still, the amount of faculties didn't exceed four up to 1919 when King Amanullah Khan came in power (1919-1929), who is branded a reorganizer and famous for his forward-looking vision within the contemporary history of Afghanistan. Hence, he's believed to be the founding father of contemporary education. Khan allowed a spread of innovations in numerous aspects of life including female education. He well-known girl schools for the first time in Afghanistan.

During Hamid Karzai's government (2001-2014), education was incredibly bloomed. per the report published by the Ministry of Education of Afghanistan (2012), there are 16,600 schools and training centers during which over ten

million students taught by 2,10,000 teachers, while the number of students at the beginning of the “Back to School” campaign in 2001 was only 900,000. However, bypassing the four-decade war, the final belief about education has significantly changed now in Afghanistan. Currently, almost every individual during this country demands a top quality education even within the agricultural areas. the foremost recent survey conducted by the center of International Cooperation (CIC, 2016) demonstrates that 96.7 percent of Afghans feel sending their children to varsities should be one in every of their priorities.

Education is that the essential foundation and a key prerequisite for long-lasting peace, stability, and socio-economic development in every society—Afghanistan isn't an exception. Development is about people, not infrastructure, geared toward bringing positive changes within the behavior and attitude of individuals.

It is for these reasons that the governments of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan prioritizes the event of education because of the key foundation for the restoration of sustainable peace, promotion of democracy, rule of law, and socio-economic development.

It's our hope and our religious, constitutional, and national duty that each Afghan child has access to quality basic education.

Quality is taken into consideration brilliant within the smallest amount the stages of the education system for all the nations of the planet. This can be because of a significant shift that the up-to-date society has made within the conceptions of data from quantity to quality. Therefore the

curriculum in schools must be associated with the immediate community, the training environment must be interesting to students, classroom learning activities must be problem-based and interactive, teaching methods should promote critical thinking skills, creativity, and innovative styles and school-based management must be tuned in to social development needs. All the above-mentioned areas of concern within the education system which is ready to bring improvement in quality of education place significant responsibility on school teachers and their professional competencies. After we take a look at the contemporary afghan education system we conclude that the quantity of education quality, teacher competencies, and student outcomes don't seem to be within the slightest degree satisfactory at any level of the education system. Therefore it must be reviewed and redefined within the contemporary education system in Afghanistan. There's a desire to bring a marked improvement within the coed learning outcomes and teacher competency levels.

Despite the foundations from various government policy documents and reports submitted by several agencies working in Afghanistan to bring improvement within the education quality, there are hardly many suitable strategies developed and implemented to boost quality within the smallest amount the levels/stages of education.

Present Situation and techniques in Afghanistan:

Afghanistan has been involved in an exceedingly serious conflict for the past four decades, therefore, the infrastructure including the tutorial infrastructure has

been seriously devastated by this long-lasting war. The foremost reasons for this problem are being described thanks to the shortage of professional teachers, lack of quality teaching-learning materials, inappropriate classroom environment, and security threats in some areas. Additionally, the studies also indicate that the standard of education is low and still the teacher-centered method is extensively utilized by Afghan school teachers and physical punishment is common in several Afghan schools. Despite some progress in training teachers, as reported by the Ministry of Education quite half the teachers haven't got the specified qualifications and effective teaching skills which are taken under consideration as an infinite challenge for quality education in Afghanistan. Especially, the shortage of qualified female teachers within the bulk of faculties located in districts is believed to be a substantial barrier to quality education.

A survey conducted by Oxfam (2011) indicates that 26.4% of people interviewed named lack of qualified female teachers because the foremost hindrance to girls' access to quality school education. Joined of the participants told to this survey that: "The lack of qualified female teachers creates many problems. Families, especially poor families, don't seem to be willing to send their daughters to highschool because they think it's a waste of resources and time, which they don't want them to possess male teachers so this becomes the rationale they're doing not send their children to highschool." there's a sort of worldwide organization like UNESCO, UNICEF, Care International, World Bank, Swedish Committee for Afghanistan (SCA), British Council and

more others are working with the Afghan government, especially together with the Ministry of Education to strengthen the professional qualifications of Afghan school teachers but still, because it's alleged by this ministry good distance is ahead to alter Afghan teachers' qualifications as they're required.

Education Problems in Afghanistan:

In the 21st century getting the following education is additionally a dream for ladies in Afghanistan, a dream which will not come true. Continuous war in some places and cultural issues are enormous challenges for Afghan women. Being an informed woman could also be an infinite achievement. After the autumn of the Taliban, Afghan women wanted to continue their studies. Visiting school after some years was an opportunity for them. We accepted visiting school under the BURQA and sat in dusty classrooms with no windows. But, after daughters to urge education.

The problem with women and education didn't simply appear during the Taliban period. Afghan women have experienced these problems for several years. Over 30 years of continuous war in Afghanistan made matters difficult. But beyond the 000 problems that prevent girls from visiting the faculty is that the culture. Culturally in Afghanistan women shouldn't get an education. they need to only occupy the house and ensure around the house. There don't seem to be any female teachers in girls' schools, girls should walk far to induce to highschool. Afghan women are full of people limited awareness. During this country providing food is additionally a priority. So I can strongly say these issues

make education a dream for them. After the autumn of the Taliban schools were reopened. Our dream looked as if it'd come true. Everyone visited the varsity. Asking during which grade you were in was the common question for all. We were happy, but this happiness for Afghan women lasted approximately two years. When the insecurity began to create problems, like threatening the girl's family, burning the colleges, women lost their hopes. Afghanistan is experiencing the Taliban period yet again, only it's worse than before. The Taliban didn't rape little girls, but nowadays small girls are being raped there thanks to school. I hope the day of our dreams and wishes can come true. For these dreams and desires, we'd like security, awareness must be broader, and also poverty should be addressed. There's some movement among the young who understand that without education we are ready to do nothing except fight. They're visiting India, Europe, and also the U.S.A. to induce education. There could even be their planes to help us to resolve education problems in Afghanistan.

Way Forward

The facts on the underside as reported by the Ministry of Education of Afghanistan highlights a selection of quality influential factors in Afghan school education like teaching methodology, qualified teachers, quality teaching/learning materials, learning environment, financial resources, and teachers' compensation, etc... Also, academic study, indicates that the quality of Afghan school education particularly lyceum education is low and one in all the key reasons for it had been inappropriate classroom teaching practice or traditional

pedagogy utilized by the bulk of Afghan school teachers. The curriculum was another quality affecting factor to be considered because it's assumed to be irrelevant to the important needs and requirements of the community. Further, the study concluded that teacher competence was still a fundamental quality influential give some thought to Afghan school education. This study has found that though the overwhelming majority of teachers who have regularly received professional training, they're did not implement effective pedagogical methods and teaching strategies in their daily classroom practices. The foremost reasons for this failure were indicated because of the dearth of self-efficacy and self-commitment for career, lack of appropriate teaching/learning facilities and lack of operative evaluation, and then the inefficiency of faculty administrations. The principals interviewed during this study underscored the importance of these mentioned quality influential factors but at the identical time they emphasized an efficient follow-up evaluation procedure which was missing at the time in Afghan schools. In step with them, the organizations that job for teacher capacity building, merely concentrate on the arrangement of more and more workshops, seminars, and other short timepieces of coaching series disregarding the evaluation of a successful implementation of those programs beyond the delivery.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the accredited organizations (governmental, non-governmental) must make more practical efforts to reinforce the quality of education in Afghanistan. Especially about the teacher

professional development programs, it's vitally important that the materials taught in these training programs should be closely related to the faculty curriculum and teacher daily classroom practices. Secondly, a shared policy is required to be formulated by the Afghan government in partnership with non-governmental organizations working within the world of education, the thanks to conduct a follow-up evaluation of the sensible impact of these programs in schools. It's to be ensured to what extent these programs can help teachers to bolster the quality of their teaching. it is also should be evaluated that what quantity better the teachers are able to apply all the teaching/learning methods and techniques, they learn in these short term training programs, in their classrooms. School administrations should be encouraged to be had for the creating of a cooperative climate in schools where

teachers can work together in respect of their professional improvement. Regarding Gregory (2008), in-service training, workshops, and other professional development programs are useful for varsity improvement, but the foremost important could be a continuous dialogue with coaches, peers, and study teams. The new National Education Strategic Plan (MOE, 2016) reports some new strategies which are formulated by the Afghan government to spice up the quality of curriculum, teachers yet as school governance. This plan considers these three, particularly teacher performance, the relevance of curriculum, and college governance thanks to the key components for quality in education. Hence, the successful implementation can help to reinforce the quality of teaching in Afghan schools.

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